

YALPI ICHKI MAHSULOT TENDENTSIYASINI EKONOMETRIK TADQIQ ETISH

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Annotatsiya: Maqolada O'zbekiston Respublikasi yalpi ichki mahsulot hajmining choraklar bo'yicha o'zgarishi vaqtli qatori modellashtirilgan. Multiplikativ model tuzish orqali YaIM hajmi kelgusi 3 yil uchun prognoz qilingan.

Kalit so'zlar: Vaqtli qator, multiplikativ model, trend, mavsumiylik.

ЭКОНОМЕТРИЧЕСКОЕ ИЗУЧЕНИЕ ТЕНДЕНЦИЙ ВАЛОВОГО ВНУТРЕННЕГО ПРОДУКТА

Аннотация: В статье моделируется временной ряд изменения объема валового внутреннего продукта Республики Узбекистан по кварталам. Путем создания мультипликативной модели был спрогнозирован объем ВВП на ближайшие 3 года.

Ключевые слова: Временной ряд, мультипликативная модель, тренд, сезонность.

AN ECONOMETRIC STUDY OF GROSS DOMESTIC PRODUCT TRENDS

Abstract: The article models the time series of changes in the volume of the gross domestic product of the Republic of Uzbekistan by quarters. By creating a multiplicative model, the volume of GDP was forecast for the next 3 years.

Key words: Time series, multiplicative model, trend, seasonality.

Ma'lumki, yalpi ichki mahsulot (YaIM) mamlakat iqtisodiyoti holatini belgilovchi eng muhim ko'rsatkichdir. Agar u barqaror o'sib borsa, bu mamlakat iqtisodiyoti rivojlanayotganini anglatadi. 2023 yil yakunlari bo'yicha O'zbekiston Respublikasi YaIM hajmi 1 066 569 mlrd so'mni tashkil etgan. Aholi jon boshiga

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29291,4 ming so'm, YaHMning o'sish surati esa 106 foiz bo'lgan. Choraklar kesimida YaHM darajalari 1-jadvalda berilgan.

1-jadval

O'zbekiston Respublikasi yalpi ichki mahsulot hajmi (mlrd so'm)¹

Yillar	Chorak	YaIM	Yillar	Chorak	YaIM
2016	I	47 816	2020	I	117 981
2016	II	114 568	2020	II	267 680
2016	III	185 110	2020	III	429 489
2016	IV	255 422	2020	IV	605 515
2017	I	53 985	2021	I	136 054
2017	II	131 713	2021	II	323 037
2017	III	221 431	2021	III	523 670
2017	IV	317 476	2021	IV	738 425
2018	I	77 923	2022	I	167 932
2018	II	187 168	2022	II	398 875
2018	III	305 271	2022	III	640 355
2018	IV	426 641	2022	IV	896 618
2019	I	98 744	2023	I	201 680
2019	II	233 452	2023	II	473 731
2019	III	380 930	2023	III	757 604
2019	IV	532 713	2023	IV	1 066 569

YaIM iqtisodiy faoliyatda eng ko'p qo'llaniladigan ko'rsatkichidir. U ma'lum bir mamlakatning iqtisodiy holatining o'sishi yoki pasayishini aniqlash, jahon iqtisodiyotini baholash va mamlakatlar iqtisodiyotini bir-biri bilan solishtirish uchun ham qo'llaniladi. Shu sababdan uning kelajakdagi qabul qilishi mumkin bo'lgan qiymatlarini prognozlash mamlakat iqtisodiyoti uchun muhim ma'lumotlarni olishga zamin yaratadi.

1-jadvalda keltirilgan vaqtli qator darajalari choraklik tendentsiyani tashkil etmoqda. Bunday vaqtli qatorlar additiv, multiplikativ, SAR, SMA, SARMA, SARIMA va boshqa turdagi regressiya tenglamalari bilan modellashtiriladi. Odatda model turini tanlashda vaqtli qator chizmasi ko'zdan kechiriladi (1-rasm).

¹ www.stat.uz - O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti huzuridagi Statistika agentligi ma'lumotlari

1-rasm. O'zbekiston Respublikasi yalpi ichki mahsulot hajmi²

1-rasmda vaqtli qator tebranish amplitudasi kengayib borayotganligini ko'rish mumkin. Demak, ushbu holatda quyidagi ko'rinishdagi multiplikativ vaqtli qator tenglamasini baholash maqsadga muvofiq:

$$Y = T \cdot S \cdot E \tag{1}$$

bu yerda, T – trend; S – mavsumiylik tarkibiy qism; E – tasodifiy xatolik.

(1) modelni baholash uchun dastlab mavsumiylikni aniqlanishimiz talab etiladi (2-jadval).

2-jadval

Mavsumiylik bahosini aniqlash bo'yicha hisob-kitoblar³

Yillar	Chorak	YaIM (Y)	Sirg'aluvchi o'rtacha	Markazlashgan sirg'aluvchi o'rtacha	Mavsumiylik bahosi
2016	I	47816,2	-	-	-
2016	II	114568,0	150729,0	-	-
2016	III	185109,8	152271,2	151500,1	1,2
2016	IV	255421,9	156557,3	154414,3	1,7
2017	I	53985,2	165637,6	161097,5	0,3
2017	II	131712,5	181151,2	173394,4	0,8
2017	III	221430,7	187135,7	184143,5	1,2
2017	IV	317476,4	200999,7	194067,7	1,6

² Muallif ishlanmasi.

³ Muallif ishlanmasi

2018	I	77923,4	221959,8	211479,8	0,4
2018	II	187168,2	249251,0	235605,4	0,8
2018	III	305271,3	254456,2	251853,6	1,2
2018	IV	426641,0	266027,1	260241,6	1,6
2019	I	98744,4	284941,8	275484,4	0,4
2019	II	233451,5	311459,7	298200,7	0,8
2019	III	380930,2	316268,8	313864,2	1,2
2019	IV	532712,5	324825,9	320547,3	1,7
2020	I	117981,0	336965,6	330895,7	0,4
2020	II	267679,7	355166,2	346065,9	0,8
2020	III	429489,1	359684,4	357425,3	1,2
2020	IV	605514,9	373523,6	366604,0	1,7
2021	I	136053,8	397068,7	385296,2	0,4
2021	II	323036,6	430296,3	413682,5	0,8
2021	III	523669,6	438265,9	434281,1	1,2
2021	IV	738425,2	457225,6	447745,8	1,6
2022	I	167932,1	486396,9	471811,3	0,4
2022	II	398875,5	525945,1	506171,0	0,8
2022	III	640354,9	534382,1	530163,6	1,2
2022	IV	896617,9	553096,0	543739,0	1,6
2023	I	201680,0	582408,2	567752,1	0,4
2023	II	473731,1	624896,0	603652,1	0,8
2023	III	757604,0	-	-	-
2023	IV	1066569,0	-	-	-

2-jadvalda keltirilgan mavsumiylik baholari o'rtacha qiymatlarini to'g'rilovchi koeffitsiyentga bo'lish orqali mavsumiylikni aniqlash mumkin (3-jadval)

3-jadval

Choraklar bo'yicha mavsumiylik tarkibiy qismi darajalari⁴

Choraklar	I	II	III	IV
JAMI	2,5	5,5	8,5	11,5

⁴ Muallif ishlanmasi

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O'rtachasi	0,354691	0,780581	1,209344	1,648744
To'g'rilovchi koeffitsiyent	0,99834			
Mavsumiylik (S)	0,355281	0,781879	1,211355	1,651485

Y natijaviy belgini (yoki (1) modelni) S ga bo'lish orqali T · E bahosi aniqlanadi:

$$\frac{Y}{S} = \frac{T \cdot S \cdot E}{S} = T \cdot E \tag{1}$$

Natijalar 4-jadvalda keltirilgan (4-jadval).

4-jadval

T · E qiymatlari⁵

Yil	Chorak	T · E	Yil	Chorak	T · E
2016	I	134 586,96	2020	I	332 078,29
2016	II	146 529,11	2020	II	342 354,38
2016	III	152 812,17	2020	III	354 552,64
2016	IV	154 661,91	2020	IV	366 648,68
2017	I	151 950,83	2021	I	382 947,09
2017	II	168 456,36	2021	II	413 154,18
2017	III	182 795,89	2021	III	432 300,78
2017	IV	192 236,88	2021	IV	447 127,97
2018	I	219 329,10	2022	I	472 674,24
2018	II	239 382,58	2022	II	510 149,78
2018	III	252 008,20	2022	III	528 627,02
2018	IV	258 337,73	2022	IV	542 916,08
2019	I	277 933,37	2023	I	567 663,55
2019	II	298 577,54	2023	II	605 887,92
2019	III	314 466,24	2023	III	625 418,74
2019	IV	322 565,71	2023	IV	645 824,13

T · E bu trend va tasodifiy xatoliklardan iborat qator hisoblanadi. Odatda bunday qatordan trendni ajratish uchun eng kichik kvadratlar usulini qo'llash etarli hisoblanadi. Shu maqsadda T = a + bt ko'rinishidagi chiziqli model tuzamiz (5-jadval).

⁵ Muallif ishlanmasi

5-jadval

Regression tahlil natijalari⁶

ВЫВОД ИТОГОВ					
<i>Регрессионная статистика</i>					
Множественный R	0,988				
R-квадрат	0,977				
Нормированный R-квадрат	0,976				
Стандартная ошибка	24 268,285				
Наблюдения	32				
Дисперсионный анализ					
	<i>df</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Значимость F</i>
Регрессия	1	7,3654E+11	7,3654E+11	1 250,606	5,131E-26
Остаток	30	1,7668E+10	588949659		
Итого	31	7,5421E+11			
	<i>Коэффициенты</i>	<i>Стандартная ошибка</i>	<i>t-статистика</i>	<i>P-Значение</i>	<i>Нижние 95%</i>
Y-пересечение	73 785,166	8 785,266	8,399	0,000	55 843,259

⁶ Muallif ishlanmasi

Переменная X 1	16	431,498	464,640	35,364	0,000	15 482,575
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5-jadvalga ko'ra, Fisherning F mezonni hisoblangan qiymati $F_{his} = 1250,606$ ga teng. Bu esa $df_1 = m = 1$ va $df_2 = n - 1 - 1 = 30$ erkinlik darajasida hamda, $\alpha = 0,05$ ahamiyatlilik darajasidagi Fisherning jadval qiymati $F_{jad} = 4.17$ dan katta. Shuningdek (3) modelning parametrlari bo'yicha Styudentning t mezonni qiymatlari $t_a = 8,399$ va $t_b = 35,364$ ga teng. Bu esa $\alpha = 0,05$ ahamiyatlilik darajasi hamda $df = n - 1 = 31$ erkinlik darajasida Styudentning t mezonni jadval qiymati $t_{jad} = 2,04$ dan katta. Shu sababli model statistik ahamiyatga ega hisoblanadi.

Shunday qilib, trend tenglamasini quyidagicha yozish mumkin:

$$T = 73785,166 + 16431,498t \tag{2}$$

Shunday qilib, S mavsumiylik tarkibiy qism darajalari hamda T trend tarkibiy qismi modeli baholandi. Ulardan foydalanib, kelgusi 3 yil uchun prognoz qiymatlar ishlab chiqildi (6-jadval). Shuni aytib o'tish kerakki, vaqtli qatorning haqiqiy darajalari hamada tekislangan darajalari o'rtasidagi approksimatsiya hatoligi 6,61 foizni tashkil etdi.

6-jadval

Yalpi ichki mahsulot hajmining 2024-2026 yillar uchun prognoz qiymatlari⁷

T/r	Yillar	Chorak	Mavsumiylik tarkibiy qismi, S	Trend tarkibiy qismi, T	Yalpi ichki mahsulot, \hat{Y}
1	2024	I	0,355281	616 024,6	218 862
2	2024	II	0,781879	632 456,1	494 504
3	2024	III	1,211355	648 887,6	786 033
4	2024	IV	1,651485	665 319,1	1 098 765
5	2025	I	0,355281	681 750,6	242 213
6	2025	II	0,781879	698 182,1	545 894
7	2025	III	1,211355	714 613,6	865 651
8	2025	IV	1,651485	731 045,1	1 207 310
9	2026	I	0,355281	747 476,6	265 564
10	2026	II	0,781879	763 908,1	597 284

⁷ Muallif ishlanmasi

11	2026	III	1,211355	780 339,6	945 268
12	2026	IV	1,651485	796 771,1	1 315 856

Prognoz qiymatlarning chizmasi 2-rasmda berilgan:

2-rasm. O'zbekiston Respublikasi yalpi ichki mahsulot hajmi (mlrd so'm)⁸

Shunday qilib, 2027 yilga kelib, O'zbekiston Respublikasi yalpi ichki mahsulot hajmi 1 315 856 mlrd so'mni, o'sish esa 123% ni tashkil etishi taxmin qilinmoqda.

FOYDALANILGAN ADABIYOTLAR RO'YXATI

1. Буранова, л. В. (2023). Повышение эффективности управления кредитными ресурсами предприятия. *O'zbekistonda fanlararo innovatsiyalar va ilmiy tadqiqotlar jurnali*, 2(19), 329-333.
2. Ergashevich, T. B. (2022). ISSUES OF SUSTAINABILITY OF DEVELOPMENT TRENDS OF THE CONSTRUCTION MATERIALS INDUSTRY OF SURKHANDARYA REGION. *Open Access Repository*, 8(12), 426-430.
3. Mamatqulova, S. F., & Turayev, B. E. (2024). Surxondaryoda to'qimachilik mahsulotlarini ishlab chiqarishni arima modeli asosida prognozlash. *Journal of Universal Science Research*, 2(1), 307-320.
4. Mamatkulova, X. N., & Turayev, B. E. (2024). Kichik biznes va xususiy tadbirkorlik subyektlarining sohalar bo'yicha tarkibiy o'zgarishlarini aniqlash orqali ularning rivojlanish darajasini o'rganish (Ryabsev indeksi). *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*, 4(3), 112-116.

⁸ Muallif ishlanmasi

ISSN (E): 2181-4570 ResearchBib Impact Factor: 6,4 / 2023 SJIF 2024 = 5.073/Volume-2, Issue-5

5. Mirzohidovna, P. M., & Turayev, B. E. (2024). Surxondaryo viloyati asosiy kapitalga kiritilgan investitsiyalar hajmini trend modellari orqali modellashtirish. *Journal of Universal Science Research*, 2(2), 296-302.
6. Субханова, М. А., & Тураев, Б. Э. (2024). Корреляционно-регрессионный анализ ликвидности коммерческих банков. *Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology*, 4(3), 38-43.
7. Tulaganova, M. H., & Turayev, B. E. (2024). Asosiy kapitalga kiritilgan investitsiyalarni trend modellari yordamida prognozlash (Surxondaryo viloyati misolida). *TECHNICAL SCIENCE RESEARCH IN UZBEKISTAN*, 2(2), 223-230.
8. Тураев, Б. (2021). Корреляционно-регрессионный анализ доли строительных работ в валовом региональном продукте Сурхандарьинской области. *Экономика и инновационные технологии*, (6), 205-214.
9. Тураев, Б. Э. (2022). Моделирование изменения цен в промышленности строительных материалов (на примере Сурхандарьинской области). In *Современные тенденции развития финансово-банковского сектора в условиях экономической неопределенности* (pp. 71-75).
10. Тўраев, Б. Э., & Хатамов, О. Қ. Арима модели ёрдамида қурилиш ишлари ҳажмини прогноз қилиш (Сурхондарё вилоятида мисолида).“ *UzBridge*” электрон журнали, 74-84.
11. То'раев, В. Е. (2024). Mahalliy byudjet daromadlarini ARIMA modeli asosida prognozlash. *Journal of Universal Science Research*, 2(1), 141-149.
12. Turaev, B. E. (2021). Forecasting the volume of construction work using the arima model (on the example of Surkhandarya region). *Scientific progress*, 2(2), 1287-1290.
13. Tuychiyeva, M. K., & Turayev, B. E. (2024). Trend modellari yordamida elektron tijorat aylanmasi hajmini modellashtirish va prognozashtirish. *Technical science research in uzbekistan*, 2(2), 193-199.
14. Xursanova, S. A., & Turayev, B. E. (2024). Hudud dehqonchilik mahsulotlari ishlab chiqarish hajmini trend modellari yordamida prognozashtirish. *Technical science research in uzbekistan*, 2(2), 200-208.
15. То'раев, В. Е. (2024). Mahalliy byudjet daromadlarini ARIMA modeli asosida prognozlash. *Journal of Universal Science Research*, 2(1), 141-149.

16. Turaev, B. E. (2021). FORECASTING THE VOLUME OF CONSTRUCTION WORK USING THE ARIMA MODEL (ON THE EXAMPLE OF SURKHANDARYA REGION). *Scientific progress*, 2(2), 1287-1290.

17. Mamatqulova, S. F., & Turayev, B. E. (2024). SURXONDARYODA TO'QIMACHILIK MAHSULOTLARINI ISHLAB CHIQRISHNI ARIMA MODELI ASOSIDA PROGNOZLASH. *Journal of Universal Science Research*, 2(1), 307-320.

18. Ibragimova, D. A., & Turayev, B. E. (2024). TURIZM SANOATINI NAZARIY TADQIQ ETISH MASALALARI. *Journal of Science-Innovative Research in Uzbekistan*, 2(2), 530-537.

19. Mamatkulova, X. N., & Turayev, B. E. (2024). KICHIK BIZNES VA XUSUSIY TADBIRKORLIK SUBYEKTLARINING SOHALAR BO'YICHA TARKIBIY O'ZGARISHLARINI ANIQLASH ORQALI ULARNING RIVOJLANISH DARAJASINI O'RGANISH (RYABSEV INDEKSI). *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*, 4(3), 112-116.

20. Khurramov, E. X. (2019). ROLE OF INNOVATION IN INCREASING EFFICIENCY OF PRODUCTION OF AGRICULTURAL PRODUCTS IN FORESTRY. *Theoretical & Applied Science*, (10), 518-521.

21. Khidirberdievich, A. E., & Mamadillayevich, Z. S. (2021). Issues of Regulation of Blockchains in the Digital Economy and World Experience in Reducing, Preventing the "Hidden Economy". *International Journal of Multicultural and Multireligious Understanding*, 8(7), 591-597.

22. Allayarov, P. (2022). The factors affecting Kyrgyzstan's bilateral trade: a gravity-model approach. *Архив научных исследований*, 4(1).

23. Ortiqov, S. M., & Mamataliyev, X. B. (2024). ECONOMETRIC ASSESSMENT OF THE EFFECT OF FIXED CAPITAL INVESTMENTS ON THE VOLUME OF AGRICULTURAL PRODUCTION. *Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology*, 4(4), 110-114.

24. Khatamov, O. K., & Ortiqov, S. M. (2019). USE FROM THE INTERNATIONAL EXPERIENCES IN EMPLOYMENT THE POPULATION IN UZBEKISTAN. *Theoretical & Applied Science*, (11), 364-371.

25. Gulnoza, E. (2024). The status of the population's use of the stock market in Uzbekistan. *Western European Journal of Linguistics and Education*, 2(4), 145-149.

26. qizi Egamnazarova, G. X. (2024). Kreditning mohiyati, asosiy funksiyalari va tashkil qilishning nazariy asoslari. *Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology*, 4(3), 748-754.
27. qizi Egamnazarova, G. X. (2024). Kredit turlari va uning ilmiy-nazariy asoslari. *Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology*, 4(3), 755-762.
28. qizi Egamnazarova, G. X. (2024). Aholi farovonligini oshirishda kredit mablag'laridan foydalanishning ilg'or xorij tajribalari. *Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology*, 4(3), 763-770.
29. Khassanov, F. O., Khuzhanazarov, U., Rakhimova, N., Esankulov, A., & Achilova, N. (2013). Two new species of Iris L.(Iridaceae Juss.) from Uzbekistan. *Stapfia*, 99, 1-3.
30. Bozorov, R. K., & Esankulov, A. E. (2019). Practice of analysis of financial stability indicators of major commercial banks in Uzbekistan. *International Journal of Advanced Science and Technology*, 28(20), 873-880.
31. Hojiqulova, F. (2022). IMPROVING THE TAX SYSTEM IN OUR COUNTRY TRAINING ISSUES. *Science and Innovation*, 1(7), 378-382.
32. Feruza, H., & Eshquvvatov, O. A. (2024). Ensuring investment activity in Uzbekistan. *Synergy: Cross-Disciplinary Journal of Digital Investigation (2995-4827)*, 2(4), 26-30.
33. Eshquvvatov, O. A., & Ilkhamovna, B. T. (2024). CORPORATE ECONOMICS AND INVESTMENTS. *Gospodarka i Innowacje.*, 46, 145-148.
34. Eshquvvatov, O. A. (2024). ACTIVATION OF THE HUMAN FACTOR IN THE INNOVATIVE ECONOMY. *Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology*, 4(3), 475-479.
35. Eshquvvatov, O. A. (2024). THE ROLE OF INFORMATION IN THE IMPLEMENTATION OF FOREIGN ECONOMIC ACTIVITY. *Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology*, 4(3), 470-474.
36. Abdugabbarovna, D. L., & Tokhtayevich, E. S. (2024). PECULIARITIES OF INCREASING THE INCOME OF THE POPULATION IN THE REGION. *Open Access Repository*, 10(1), 74-77.
37. Abdugabbarovna, D. L., & Samandarovich, I. E. (2024). IMPROVEMENT OF THE ORGANIZATIONAL AND LEGAL BASIS OF

ISSN (E): 2181-4570 ResearchBib Impact Factor: 6,4 / 2023 SJIF 2024 = 5.073/Volume-2, Issue-5

MICROFINANCING OF SMALL BUSINESS AND PRIVATE ENTREPRENEURSHIP. *Open Access Repository*, 10(1), 65-68.

38. Abdugabbarovna, D. L., & Abdurashidovich, A. O. (2024). THE ROLE OF SMALL BUSINESS AND PRIVATE ENTREPRENEURSHIP IN ENSURING THE EMPLOYMENT OF THE POPULATION AND INCREASING THEIR INCOME. *Open Access Repository*, 10(1), 54-57.

39. Abdugabbarovna, D. L. (2024). PECULIARITIES OF SMALL BUSINESS AND PRIVATE ENTREPRENEURSHIP DEVELOPMENT. *Open Access Repository*, 10(1), 50-53.

40. Abdugabbarovna, D. L., & Choriyevena, S. N. (2023). THE ROLE OF INVESTMENT AND PREFERENTIAL LOANS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF SMALL BUSINESS ENTITIES. *Open Access Repository*, 9(11), 35-38.

41. Solijonovna, S. R. (2021). Export-oriented localization as a key factor in import substitution. *World Bulletin of Social Sciences*, 5, 36-39.

42. Sobitova, R. N. S. (2020). SCIENTIFIC AND THEORETICAL BASES OF LOCALIZATION OF INDUSTRIAL PRODUCTION. *Theoretical & Applied Science*, (10), 401-406.

43. Sobitova, R. N. S. (2020). LOCALIZATION OF PRODUCTION AS A TOOL OF MODERNIZATION. *Theoretical & Applied Science*, (10), 407-411.

44. Solidjonovna, S. R. (2024). The role of localization of production in the stable and consistent development of the economy. *Web of Scientists and Scholars: Journal of Multidisciplinary Research*, 2(3), 1-4.

45. Solijonovna, S. R. (2023). Import Replacement-As an Assistant Mechanism for Diversification of Production and Approval of Foreign Trade.

46. Sultonov, X. G. (2022). EFFECTIVENESS OF ATTRACTING INVESTMENTS IN IMPROVING THE ECOLOGICAL CONDITION OF IRRIGATED LANDS. *Экономика и социум*, (4-1 (95)), 56-60.

47. Алтиев, А. С., Очилов, И. С., & Султонов, Х. Ф. (2021). GLOBAL EXPERIENCES IN IMPROVING THE ECONOMIC MECHANISMS OF IRRIGATED LAND IMPROVEMENT. *Экономика и социум*, (6-1), 418-426.

48. Allayor o'g'li, X. R. (2023). GLOBALLASHUV SHAROITIDA HUDUDNING EKSPORT SALOHIYATINI YANADA TAKOMILLASHTIRISH YO'NALISHLARI. *Journal of Universal Science Research*, 1(6), 799-803.

49. Allayor o'g'li, X. R. (2023). HUDUDNING EKSPORT SALOHIYATINI STATISTIK TADQIQ QILISH VA EKONOMETRIK MODELLASHTIRISH (SURXONDARYO VILOYATI MISOLIDA). *O'ZBEKISTONDA FANLARARO INNOVATSIYALAR VA ILMIY TADQIQOTLAR JURNALI*, 2(20), 753-755.
50. Norqobilov, N. (2020). The role of foreign investment in the development of the economy of Kashkadarya region. *Business Expert*, 1, 145.
51. Norqobilov, N., & Abdullayev, J. (2023). Specific features of solving the housing problem in our country in the context of economic reforms. *Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology*, 3(2), 21-23.
52. Norqobilov, N., & Rasulov, F. (2023). THE ROLE OF SOCIAL PROTECTION IN IMPROVING THE LIVING WELL-BEING OF THE POPULATION. *Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology*, 3(2), 24-25.
53. Norkobilov, N. N. (2021). Structure and features of expanding investment in the southern region of uzbekistan. *Asian Journal of Research in Social Sciences and Humanities*, 11(11), 704-709.

